

SEARCH FOR NEW ANTIMALARIALS: SYNTHESIS OF SOME SUBSTITUTED 1:2-DIHYDRO-*s*-TRIAZINES. PART I

BY A. B. SEN AND P. R. SINGH

Twenty five 1:2-dihydro-*s*-triazines have been synthesised by two different methods with a view to testing their antimalarial activity.

Following the discovery of the antimalarial, proguanil (Curd *et al.*, *Ann. Trop. Med. Parasitol.*, 1945, 39, 208), a large number of biguanides have been synthesised and tested as possible antimalarials. Amongst these, the sulphabiguanides were found to possess the highest activity (Bami *et al.*, *J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1949, 31A, 1; Singh *et al.*, *Ind. J. Malar.*, 1950, 4, 455; Curd *et al.*, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1950, 5, 438; Misra *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14C, 173). Detailed investigations on the mechanism of action of proguanil have revealed that its antimalarial action is due to the formation of a metabolite in the host. Out of the three metabolites isolated, 4:6-diamino-1-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-2:2-dimethyl-1:2-dihydro-*s*-triazine was found to be ten times as active as proguanil (Crouse *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 492; Carrington *et al.*, *Nature*, 1951, 168, 1080). This led to the synthesis of a large number of 1:2-dihydro-*s*-triazines (I), which were found to possess useful therapeutic activity against a number of different types of diseases (Modest *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 855; Foley *et al.*, Proc. 52nd General Meeting of the Society of American Bacteriologists, Boston, Mass, May 1, 1952, p. 63; Farber *et al.*, *Am. J. Pathol.*, 1952, 28, 559; Foley, *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1953, 83, 733, 740, 742; Farber *et al.*, *Proc. Am. Assoc. Cancer Res.*, 1953, 1, 15; Hewitt *et al.*, *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.*, 1954, 3, 225; Lux, "Antibiotics and Chemotherapy", 1954, Vol. 4, p. 971; Foley, Thesis Universiteit van Leeu wenhoek, 1955; Raychaudhuri, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 75).

From the results of the antimalarial activity of 1:2-dihydro-*s*-triazines reported, it can be concluded that halogen-substituted 1:2-dihydro-*s*-triazines are generally very active (Singh *et al.*, *Ind. J. Malar.*, 1954, 8, 1; Bami, *Curr. Sci.*, 1954, 23, 124; Misra *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Amongst these, 4:6-diamino-1-(*p*-bromophenyl)-2:2-dimethyl-1:2-dihydro-*s*-triazine (I: R = *p*-Br; R₁ = R₂ = Me) is twice as active as the corresponding *para*-chloro derivative (I: R = *p*-Cl; R₁ = R₂ = Me) and 3:4-dichloro compound (I: R = 3:4-dichloro-; R₁ = R₂ = Me) is several times more active than the corresponding 2:4-dichloro derivative (I: R = 2:4-dichloro-; R₁ = R₂ = Me). On the other hand, the replacement of the two methyl groups in position-2 (I: R₁ & R₂) by heavier groups results in considerable loss of activity. Thus, it is apparent that the nature, number and position of the substituents have a profound influence on the antimalarial activity of the dihydrotriazines.

The present investigation has therefore been undertaken with the object of studying the structure-activity relationship in substituted 1:2-dihydro-*s*-triazines. The dihydrotriazines containing *p*-OMe, *p*-OEt, *o*-Cl, *m*-Cl, *p*-Cl, 2:4-dichloro-, *o*-Et, *p*-Me, 2:4- and 2:6-Me, *p*-OH-Ph.C₆H₄ groups at position-1 and *p*-OMe.C₆H₄, *p*-OH.C₆H₄-

and groups at position-2 have been isolated in the form of their

hydrochlorides by (i) the Three Component synthesis and (ii) the Two Component synthesis, described by Modest *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, 21, 14; Abstract of papers, 122nd Meeting, American Chemical Society, Atlantic City, N. J., September 16, 1952, p. 9-L) and have been sent to the Malaria Institute of India, Delhi for the evaluation of the antimalarial activity.

The dihydrotriazines have been distinguished from the arylbiguanides by the non-formation of a coloured complex with cuprammonium sulphate, a test for biguanide type of grouping that involves chelation at N² and N⁴.

(I)

(II)

The identification of the dihydrotriazines (I), prepared, and their distinction from the isomeric structures (II) and from the unchanged arylbiguanides, were made by means of the characteristic ultraviolet absorption spectra of these substances. The ultraviolet absorption maxima in some typical cases (I : R = *p*-OEt, R₁ = H, R₂ = *p*-MeO.C₆H₄- ; I : R = *p*-Cl, R₁ = H, R₂ = *p*-OMe.C₆H₄- ; I : R = *p*-OMe, R₁ = H, R₂ = *p*-HO.C₆H₄- ; I : R = *p*-Me ; R₁ = H ; R₂ = *p*-HO.C₆H₄- ; I : R = 2:4-

dichloro, R₁ & R₂ = and, I : R = *o*-Et, R₁ & R₂ =

 with 0.00008% aqueous solutions, were obtained at 241-242 mμ,

which are in a region characteristic for the dihydrotriazines (I) and are quite out of the range for those of structure (II) with maxima at 255 mμ (Modest, *loc. cit.*, p. 1) and the biguanide structure with maxima at 266-67 mμ (Raychaudhuri, *loc. cit.*). From the above observations it may be concluded that the compounds prepared are pure dihydrotriazines with the structure (I).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

1 : 2-Dihydro-*s*-triazines were obtained by the two methods of Modest *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) given below :

(i). *The Three Component Synthesis.*—A mixture of the substituted aniline hydrochloride (0.1 *M*), dicyandiamide (0.17 *M*) and the aldehyde or ketone (0.15-0.2 *M*) in 95% ethanol (50 c.c.) was refluxed with stirring on a water-bath for nearly 17 hours. The reaction mixture usually became coloured and crystals separated on cooling. The crystalline dihydrotriazine derivative was filtered, washed and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds, thus prepared, are listed in Table I.

(ii). *The Two Component Synthesis.*—In this reaction arylbiguanides were condensed with aldehydes or ketones in acidic medium. A mixture of the substituted aniline hydrochloride (0.1 *M*) and dicyandiamide (0.1 *M*) in water (20-25 c.c.) was refluxed for 1-1½ hours. The precipitate obtained on cooling was filtered and recrystallised from water. The *N*¹-*p*-OMe, *N*¹-*p*-OEt-, *N*¹-*o*-Cl-, *N*¹-*m*-Cl-, *N*¹-*p*-Cl-, *N*¹-2 : 4-dichloro-, *N*¹-*p*-Me-, *N*¹-*o*-Et-, *N*¹-2 : 4-dimethyl-, *N*¹-2 : 6-dimethyl-, and *N*¹-OH-phenylbiguanide hydrochlorides, thus obtained, have been used as intermediates for the synthesis of dihydrotriazines.

Condensation of Biguanides with the Aldehydes or the Ketones.—The condensation between the biguanide hydrochlorides and the aldehydes or the ketones to form the dihydrotriazines was most successful in a weakly acidic medium. Although hydrochloric acid is the acid of choice, other strong inorganic and organic acids like nitric, picric or acetic acid could also be used with success. A mixture of the substituted arylbiguanide (0.1 *M*), HCl (conc., 0.15-0.2 *M*) and the aldehyde or the ketone (0.105-0.2 *M*) in absolute ethanol (50-60 c.c.) was refluxed with stirring on a water-bath. The condensation was complete when the reaction mixture no longer gave a coloured precipitate with cuprammonium sulphate (negative biguanide test). The time required for the completion of the reaction was usually 8 hours for the aldehydes and 17 hours for the ketones, after which the reaction mixture was cooled in ice and the precipitate thus obtained was filtered, washed and recrystallised from ethanol. Occasionally the dihydrotriazine separated as a dihydrochloride in this reaction, but was converted into the monohydrochloride by recrystallisation from 50% ethanol or water. The 1 : 2-dihydro-*s*-triazines, prepared by this method, are listed in Table I.

Picrates.—Crystalline picrates of 1 : 2-dihydro-*s*-triazines were readily obtained on mixing hot saturated aqueous or alcoholic solutions of picric acid and the particular dihydrotriazine. These picrates are listed in Table I.

Nitrites.—A solution of sodium nitrite (0.015*M*) in water (5 c. c.) was added to a solution of the dihydrotriazine hydrochloride (0.015 *M*) in water (100 c.c.). Shortly after addition small crystals of 1 : 2 dihydrotriazine nitrite separated from the solution. After 3-5 hours, the product was filtered and washed with water. The nitrites listed in Table II melted with effervescence. Recrystallisation from hot water gave white prisms without any change in the melting points.

TABLE I
 (Vide formula I)

No.	R =	M.P.	*Yield.		% Nitrogen.		M.P.	Picrates		% Nitrogen.	
			(i).	(ii).	Found.	Calc.		Formula.	Found.		Calc.
			$R_1 = p\text{-MeO}, C_6H_4; R_2 = H$								
1.	<i>p</i> -OMe	219-20°	56%	61%	19.43	19.36	160°	$C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_6$	20.17	20.21	
2.	<i>p</i> -OEt	207-208°	63	88	18.48	18.64	167-68°	$C_{24}H_{24}O_4N_6$	19.66	19.72	
3.	<i>o</i> -Cl	206-207°	51	52	18.89	19.13	160-61°	$C_{22}H_{18}O_4N_6Cl$	19.99	20.05	
4.	<i>m</i> -Cl	232°	60	63	19.07	19.13	136-37°	$C_{22}H_{18}O_4N_6Cl$	19.89	20.05	
5.	<i>p</i> -Cl	234-35°	53	56	19.00	19.13	185°	$C_{22}H_{18}O_4N_6Cl$	19.97	20.05	
6.	2 : 4-Di-Cl	214-15°	57	59	17.35	17.50	227°	$C_{21}H_{16}O_4N_6Cl_2$	18.75	18.88	
7.	<i>p</i> -Me	215-16°	53	58	20.01	20.26	220°	$C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_6$	20.77	20.81	
8.	<i>o</i> -Et	217°	48	56	19.41	19.47	145°	$C_{23}H_{24}O_4N_6$	20.13	20.29	
9.	2 : 4-Di-Me	211.12°	41	40	19.29	19.47	187°	$C_{24}H_{24}O_4N_6$	20.27	20.29	
10.	2 : 6-Di-Me	199°	43	42	19.30	19.47	131°	$C_{24}H_{24}O_4N_6$	20.21	20.29	
11.	<i>p</i> -OH	229-30°	55	54	19.97	20.15	231-32°	$C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_6$	20.65	20.74	
			$R_1 = p\text{-HO}, C_6H_4; R_2 = H$								
12.	<i>p</i> -OMe	206-207°	58	51	20.02	20.15	140°	$C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_6$	20.68	20.74	
13.	<i>p</i> -OEt	231-32°	47	58	19.26	19.36	131-32°	$C_{24}H_{24}O_4N_6$	20.16	20.21	
14.	<i>o</i> -Cl	221-22°	44	47	19.83	19.88	128°	$C_{21}H_{17}O_4N_6Cl$	20.48	20.56	
15.	<i>m</i> -Cl	292-93°	39	42	19.77	19.88	255°	$C_{21}H_{17}O_4N_6Cl$	20.51	20.56	
16.	<i>p</i> -Cl	253-54°	42	49	19.85	19.88	193-94°	$C_{21}H_{17}O_4N_6Cl$	20.44	20.56	
17.	2 : 4-Di-Cl	198-200°	53	53	17.96	18.11	133°	$C_{21}H_{16}O_4N_6Cl_2$	19.12	19.34	
18.	<i>p</i> -Me	222-23°	50	53	21.00	21.12	148-49°	$C_{22}H_{20}O_4N_6$	21.36	21.37	
19.	<i>o</i> -Et	297-98°	39	42	20.17	20.26	246-47°	$C_{23}H_{24}O_4N_6$	20.67	20.81	
20.	2 : 4-Di-Me	241-42°	40	44	20.14	20.26	263°	$C_{23}H_{24}O_4N_6$	20.78	20.81	
21.	<i>p</i> -OH	296-97°	45	44	20.86	20.99	188-89°	$C_{21}H_{16}O_4N_6$	21.10	21.29	

TABLE I (Contd.)
(Vide formula I)

No.	R=	M.P.	*Yield,		% Nitr.-gen.		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
			(i),	(ii),	Found,	Calc.			Found,	Calc.
22.	<i>o</i> -Cl	251-52°	71%	89%	21.31	21.34	164-65°	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₇ N ₆ Cl	21.48	21.53
23.	2 : 4-Di-Cl	240-42°	70	85	19.20	19.31	206-207°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₇ N ₆ Cl ₂	20.06	20.18
24.	<i>p</i> -Et	227-28°	67	88	20.88	20.96	188-90°	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₇ N ₆	21.69	21.78
25.	<i>p</i> -OH	275-76°	62	81	22.57	22.61	201-202°	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₈ N ₆	22.22	22.31

* (i) By Three Component Synthesis.

(ii) Re Two Component Synthesis.

TABLE II

Comp.	Formula.	M.P.		% Nitrogen.		Bicarbonates		% Hydrogen.	
		Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
2	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₆	153°	21.55	21.76	56.73	56.86	5.66	5.74	
4	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₆ Cl	166°	22.24	22.31	51.89	52.11	4.51	4.60	
13	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₆	155°	22.48	22.59	55.84	55.83	5.44	5.43	
18	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₆	147°	24.51	24.56	57.01	57.14	5.36	5.32	
23	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₆ Cl ₂	161°	22.47	22.52	46.29	46.40	4.85	4.90	
24	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₆	167°	23.28	23.31	58.75	58.79	7.08	7.21	

* See Table I.

Bicarbonates.—The 1:2-dihydrotriazine bicarbonates were prepared by mixing the saturated aqueous solutions of sodium bicarbonate and the dihydrotriazine hydrochloride in the ratio of 1:2 by volume and refrigerating the clear solution overnight. White or colorless crystals thus obtained were filtered and washed with water. The bicarbonates, thus prepared, are listed in Table II.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received March 31, 1958.